

X-ray Studies on "Decomposed Clathrates"

V. M. Bhatnagar

The X-ray powder diffraction patterns of five 'decomposed clathrates' have been measured. The four compounds, viz., VM, HM, NJ, and QR, show almost similar patterns and only LP shows other pattern. It is assumed that these complexes may be clathrate compounds reported by Rayner and Powell.

Hofmann and Höchtlen¹ described the preparation of a few complexes, now known as clathrates. They showed that when benzene was added to a solution of nickel cyanide in aqueous ammonia and containing acetic acid, a precipitate of the composition $[\text{Ni}(\text{CN})_2 \cdot \text{NH}_3 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_6]$ was formed. Similar complexes are produced by aniline, furan, phenol, pyridine, pyrrole, and thiophene².

EXPERIMENTAL

These clathrates were prepared in our laboratories by the method adopted by Hofmann and Höchtlen¹. Several times the wrong analysis was obtained and later it was found that we might have obtained some of the hydrated forms of clathrates³ or the right compounds which then decomposed in the way they described. The former statement is not true as the present results do not agree with the various formulas of hydrated nickel cyanide-ammonia complexes found in our laboratories⁴⁻⁸. The statement has been found, however, true in the attempted preparation of furan clathrate⁹. Another compound, obtained as described by the present worker⁹, on analysis gave: C, 18.61%; H, 2.87%; N, 29.96%. Rayner and Powell³ found: C, 18.5%; H, 2.9%; N, 30.6% in hydrated nickel cyanide-ammonia complex $[\text{Ni}(\text{CN})_2 \cdot \text{NH}_3 \cdot \frac{1}{2}\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ on analysis.

The X-ray powder diffraction patterns of five samples (mentioned here as VM, NJ, HM, LP, and QR) of these "decomposed clathrates" were recorded automatically with

1. Hofmann and Höchtlen, *Ber.*, 1903, **36**, 1149.
2. Hofmann and Arnoldi, *ibid.*, 1906, **39**, 339.
3. Rayner and Powell, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 3412.
4. Bhatnagar, in Press.
5. Bhatnagar and Cloutier, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1962, **40**, 1708.
6. Bhatnagar and Fujiwara, *Chem. & Ind.*, 1962, 1471.
7. Nakajima, Bhatnagar and Cole, *J. Phys. Soc., Japan*, 1962, **17**, 1194.
8. Bhatnagar and Cole, unpublished work.
9. Bhatnagar, this *Journal*, 1962, **39**, 143.

X-ray diffractometer of Rickermann Seifert Isodebeyflex Model II, and showed the intensity of X-ray measured by Geiger counter in the ordinate and the refraction angle Θ in the abscissa.

The calculated analysis of the original (undecomposed) clathrates and determined compositions of "decomposed clathrates" are recorded in Table I. $d_{calc.}$ are obtained according to the equation:

$$d_{calc.} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{\frac{h^2 + k^2}{a^2} + \frac{l^2}{c^2}}}$$

where a and c are the lattice constants and are assumed to be the same as those reported by Rayner and Powell¹⁰ ($a=7.24 \text{ \AA}$ and $c=8.27 \text{ \AA}$).

TABLE I

% Carbon.		% Hydrogen.		% Nitrogen.	
VM ("Decomposed clathrate" of benzene).					
Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
53.20	46.60	3.87	4.37	22.45	20.40
NJ ("Decomposed clathrate" of benzene).					
41.73	..	4.32	..	21.73	..
HM ("Decomposed clathrate" of thiophene).					
30.41	34.01	3.44	3.30	21.80	19.83
LP ("Decomposed clathrate" of pyridine).					
38.21	44.21	3.08	2.63	18.76	22.26
QR ("Decomposed clathrate" of pyrrole).					
31.90	36.92	3.83	4.10	26.40	28.76

DISCUSSION

The present work has been undertaken to investigate the latter statement about the "decomposed clathrates" whether they show any resemblance to original group of clathrates or they belong to a new class of inclusion compounds.

The diffraction patterns indicate that "decomposed clathrates" VM, NJ, HM, and QR have similar crystal lattices and so almost the same molecular configuration in crystals, although these compounds constitute a different composition.

To identify these compounds with clathrates, spacing d of dicyanosamminenickelbenzene complex, reported by Rayner and Powell¹⁰, have been calculated from their data and these values agree well with the observed values of our compounds recorded in Table II. From these data, it is assumed that these "decomposed clathrates" are of the same type of clathrates as reported by Rayner and Powell¹⁰.

FIG. 1

TABLE II

Observed pattern.			Indexing of the observed pattern according to Powell's clathrate structure ¹⁰ .		
Θ .	$d_{\text{obs.}}$	Intensity.	(hkl) ¹⁰ .	$d_{\text{calc.}}$	Intensity (observed by Powell).
5.35	8.27 Å	s	001	8.28 Å	s
			100	7.25	..
			101	5.45	..
			110	5.125	..
8.65	5.13		111	4.355	s
10.10	4.395	vs	002	4.14	vs
10.70	4.15	vs	200	3.62	vs
12.30	3.62	s	102	3.595	m
			201	3.32	..
13.75	3.24	s	120	3.24	..
			112	3.22	..
			201	3.32	..
			121	3.02	..
14.80	3.02				
15.10	2.96				
15.55	2.88				
16.15	2.77	s	003	2.76	vs
			202	2.73	..
16.55	2.705	..	103	2.58	..
17.55	2.56	Shoulder	220	2.56	vs
17.60	2.55	vs	122	2.55	..
18.40	2.44	s	113	2.43	s
			300	2.415	..
19.20	2.345*	..	221	2.38	vs
			301	2.32	m
19.70	2.29	..	130	2.29	..
20.50	2.20	vs	131	2.21	..
			203	2.195	s
			222	2.18	s
21.70	2.065		123	2.10	..
			302	2.09	m*
			004	2.07	vs
22.00	2.06	..			
22.40	2.02*				
22.60	2.005		220	2.01	..
			132	2.005	..
			104	1.990	m
23.55	1.929		231	1.952	..
			114	1.919	s
24.20	1.881		223	1.878	v*
			303	1.818	..
25.20	1.811	..	400	1.811	s
			232	1.808	..
25.40	1.797		204	1.798	m
25.80	1.771		401	1.775	s
			133	1.764	..
			140	1.759	..
			124	1.745	..
			141	1.719	v*

TABLE II (contd.)

Observed pattern.			Indexing of the observed pattern according to Powell's clathrate structure.		
θ .	d_{obs} .	Intensity.	(hkl) ¹⁰ .	d_{calc} .	Intensity* (observed by Powell).
28.90	1.704		330	1.708	vs
27.80	1.864		331	1.673	vs
			402	1.658	vs
			005	1.656	vs
			233	1.625	
			142	1.618	
			105	1.618	
			240	1.614	
			224	1.610	
			241	1.590	

*These lines might be (111) and (200) lines of aluminium used as the sample holder, respectively.

The author is indebted to Dr. H. Mima, Takeda Pharmaceutical Industries, Ltd., Osaka (Japan), for the X-ray measurements. Grateful acknowledgement is made to the University of Western Australia for financial support.

DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
THE UNIVERSITY OF WESTERN AUSTRALIA,
NEDLANDS, PERTH (AUSTRALIA).

Received April 28, 1962.